

Peculiarities of marketing of financial services

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Abstract

Marketing of financial services refers to using various marketing strategies to attract new customers and retain old ones. The objectives of marketing financial services are to recognize the peculiarity of the field of action, adapt to the changing outer conditions of the market, and increase the competitiveness in the market, which will boost the profits to realize the consumers' expectations and the providers of the service. This review has found that the peculiarities in marketing in the financial sector differ culturally and geographically. The financial sectors like banks, insurance companies have to keep up the competitive Advantage to be relevant. It has been elicited in this review that the consumers can be educated about the financial products via advertising and banking sector, and the insurance part can come together as a co-operating unit to satisfy the economic needs of the consumer.

Keywords: Financial Services, Marketing, Peculiarities

Introduction

Marketing of financial services refers to using various marketing strategies to attract new customers and retain old ones. The peculiarity of the marketing financial services approach differs among the type of product being sold and makes it stand out in the multitudes of similar products.

The objectives of marketing financial services are to recognize the peculiarity of the field of action, adapt to the changing outer conditions of the market, and increase the competitiveness in the market, which will boost the profits to realize the expectations of the consumers and the providers of the service (Razyberg et al., 2006).

Shkarlet et al. (2018) have elaborated on improving the financial services market as it helps develop the country's economic development. The basis of the financial market is establishing investment and credit resources that enhance the economy segment.

This study was conducted in Ukraine. It was found that investigating the determinants of the financial services' peculiarities enhanced the transparency of the functioning of the market both for the consumer and the provider; it helped increase the financial literacy and augmented the stability of the financial institution.

The marketing managers have to make an effort to understand the peculiarities in the consumer's behavior and their purchasing choices (Kotler, 2001). Therefore this review plans to study the various nuances of marketing of financial services.

Literature Review

Heinemann and Jopp (2002) found that the idiosyncrasies like language and geographical differences, different taxation laws in different countries, dissimilar consumer protection prearrangement were some of the obstacles in marketing financial products. These peculiarities are mostly seen with foreign insurance products, internet-centered financial retail, credit business, and pension products.

Arych (2019) has expanded on the concept of peculiarities in the insurance sector in Ukraine. The insurance market is a significant component of the financial markets as it is a sign of a steady national economic development. The marketing strategies have moved from production and firm-oriented product to consumer-oriented needs, i.e., it has to be tailored to the consumer's wants. For example, life insurance policies have to maintain their market share and compete with pension funds, banks, etc. They have to use innovative methods like progressive technology to keep themselves relevant to the consumer and generate profits.

Kostogryz and Sokolenko (2017) have explained the banking sector's peculiarities, which has a foremost position in the financial markets. Banks not only have to compete with other banks for their products and services like savings and lending's they offer, but they also have to compete with other non-banking institutions like credit companies, insurance companies, pawnshops, pension funds, investment funds, post offices, etc. who have flexible and simplified financial schemes. In Ukraine, banks have entered into business with insurance companies to expand their arena of activity and mollify consumers' economic needs.

Marketing in the present global scenario has to face long-lasting survival challenges and compete with the other to maintain their consumer base by being creative in their approach (Zostautiene and Daraskeviciute., 2009). *Competitive Advantage* is one of the most imperative factors of marketing strategies (Korsakiene, 2004). The different aspects of competitive Advantage are the assortment of services, price, quality of service and the product, etc. Competitive Advantage gives distinct features to the company making them unique and ahead of the average company and forms a distinctive relationship with the suppliers and the consumer to satisfy the consumer's needs (Jewell, 2002).

Shybakovska (2014) has particularized a study in Ukraine on the peculiarities of advertising on the domestic banking services. Advertising of banking products is to stimulate demand to attract new clients. It provides knowledge to the consumers about its services and products such as credit cards, electronic banking, and more than fifty percent of the advertising is done through television, internet marketing, radio, press, etc.

A study done in Russia has explained the situation on the ground regarding the financial markets are lagging in their development due to the low creditworthiness of the consumers and their distrust in Russia's financial market. The consumers' low creditworthiness is attributed to climatic and geographical conditions, poorly developed communication, and lending. In Russia, the financial services are marketed more for profitability and less for social improvement. Even though Russia has a robust, well-developed financial market, only forty-five percent of the Russians are aware of deposit insurance; sixty percent believe in banking services, and 35% in insurance products and services (Vinogradova, 2018).

Mutandwa and Kwiringirimana (2015) have illustrated the factors affecting the choice of opening a bank account rural bank in Rwanda are education and farm size, and these determinants can be used by financial service market managers in extending services tailored to their needs. Radio advertisements in the local language, the community meets, social networks helped the consumer gain awareness of the banks' financial services. In rural areas, the consumer relies on the image, reputation, and quality of services and less on deposit rates of the bank, and on the contrary, in developed countries, the banks use internet banking or electronic banking as a mode of enhancing their financial services. Deposit rates, security, computer skills, service quality, gender, and education are determinants of doing business with the bank by the consumer.

Raju(1995) has elaborated that the consumers in developing countries differ on the adoption of technology and the consumer purchasing behavior, and he has coined his theory as ABCD (Access, Buying Behaviour, Consumer Characteristics, and Disposal). Service quality, interest rates, and location are important determinants of a selection of financial services from banks even in Ghana, South Africa, India, and Malaysia (Mutandwa and Kwiringirimana, 2015).

The peculiarities of marketing of financial services

Based on the literature reviewed in the earlier paragraph, we enlist the peculiarities of marketing of financial services as under:

1. Building trust is a must
2. Educating the prospective customer about their financial well-being
3. Make effective use of influencing personalities
4. Relate well with the target audience
5. Offering customized solutions

This by no means is an exhaustive list. However, by and large, these peculiarities are quite distinct when it comes to marketing financial services. Customers are often having either of the two extreme mentalities – one driven by fear and anxiety while the other is influenced by greed. Genuine efforts are required to bring the prospective customer to the "middle-of-the-road" through counseling and education.

Conclusion

This review has found that the peculiarities in marketing in the financial sector differ culturally and geographically. The financial sectors like banks, insurance companies have to keep up the competitive Advantage to be relevant. It has been elicited in this review that the consumers can be educated about the financial products via advertising and banking sector, and the insurance part can come together as a co-operating unit to satisfy the economic needs of the consumer. It is all about attracting new customers and retaining the old ones.

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